

Original Research

The Role of Zakat Dedication as a Tax Incentive in Enhancing Compliance and Achieving Financial Justice

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of recognizing zakat deductibility from income tax to enhance zakat compliance and promote fiscal justice in Yemen. Drawing on the Tax Incentive Theory, Fiscal Justice Theory, Legal Commitment Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the study explores five key predictors: legislation, financial burden, administrative procedures, community awareness, and ethical alignment. A total of 401 valid responses were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Findings indicate a strong and significant impact of zakat deductibility on compliance behavior ($\beta = 0.744$, $R^2 = 0.554$, $f^2 = 1.242$, $Q^2 = 0.550$, $p < 0.001$). Administrative procedures emerged as the most influential factor ($\beta = 0.402$), while legislation ($\beta = 0.116$) and awareness ($\beta = 0.113$) showed smaller yet significant effects. These results highlight the importance of transparent, simplified, and technology-enabled systems in promoting voluntary compliance. The study contributes to Islamic fiscal literature and offers policy guidance for integrating zakat within national tax systems in fragile contexts. Key recommendations include digitizing zakat registration, aligning zakat and tax policies, and enhancing outreach in underserved areas.

Keywords: Compliance, fiscal justice, legal commitment, PLS-SEM, tax deduction, tax incentive, Yemen, Zakat.

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Introduction

Zakat, one of the five pillars of Islam, has historically served as a mechanism for wealth redistribution and the promotion of social justice. Despite its spiritual prominence, institutional compliance with zakat obligations, particularly in fragile states, remains a critical challenge. As emphasized in the Qur'anic verse: “Take alms from their wealth to purify and sanctify them, and pray for them. Verily, your prayer is a source of comfort for them. And Allah is All-Hearing, All-Knowing.” (Qur'an, Surah At-Tawbah, 9:103) (*Qur'an, Surah At-Tawbah, 9:103*)

This verse encapsulates both the spiritual and socio-economic dimensions of zakat, highlighting its dual role in personal purification and societal stability.

While many studies have explored zakat integration in stable contexts like Malaysia and Indonesia, where tax deductibility has proven effective in enhancing compliance, such experiences are not directly transferable to states with institutional fragility.

In Yemen, despite the strong religious and cultural significance of zakat, formal compliance remains low. This is largely due to the lack of legislative incentives, procedural complexity, and widespread distrust in public financial institutions. This raises the study's central research question: Can integrating zakat into Yemen's tax system, as a deductible expense, enhance compliance and promote fiscal justice?

This study is distinct in its focus on a conflict-affected Islamic context, where religious and economic motives intersect under conditions of weak governance. It employs four theoretical frameworks: Tax Incentive Theory, Fiscal Justice Theory, Legal Commitment Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior, to examine the multifaceted drivers of zakat compliance.

This research analyzes the impact of zakat deductibility through five predictive constructs: legislation, financial burden, administrative procedures, community awareness, and ethical alignment and addresses a significant gap in the Islamic finance literature and offering actionable insights for policymakers operating in fragile environments.

Zakat as a Tax Deductible

Numerous studies conducted in Malaysia and Indonesia have highlighted the effectiveness of zakat deductibility as a financial incentive for promoting voluntary compliance (Halim et al., 2025; Samad et al., 2016; Wijayanti et al., 2022). In these contexts, clearly defined legal frameworks, administrative transparency, and awareness campaigns played a significant role in aligning religious obligations with fiscal policies. However, these models were implemented in stable countries with functioning institutions—conditions that do not apply to Yemen.

Conversely, experiences from other Muslim-majority countries have revealed more complex outcomes. In Pakistan, (Iqbal & Anwar, 2021) found that tax incentives improved compliance, but their effect was limited in regions with weak law enforcement. In Iran, such incentives were associated with an increase in the number of registered

taxpayers, thereby boosting government revenues (Ameli et al., 2025). In Turkey, (Dönmez & Cural, 2025) demonstrated that zakat deductibility enhanced compliance only when accompanied by transparency reforms. In Nigeria, researchers such as (Kodifikasi et al., 2018; Ummulkhayr, 2018; Ummulkhayr et al., 2020) emphasized the critical role of religious legitimacy and administrative efficiency. These varied findings underscore that zakat deductibility is not a one-size-fits-all instrument; rather, its effectiveness depends on precise alignment with local contexts. In Saudi Arabia, for example, recent analyses suggest that the success of zakat as a fiscal incentive is heavily contingent upon administrative quality, regulatory frameworks, and integration with broader fiscal policies (Asadov et al., 2024; Nuruddin et al., 2023). In Uzbekistan, the study by (Asadov et al., 2024) offered key policy recommendations, including the implementation of tax incentives for zakat and the enhancement of public awareness regarding zakat.

Despite these insights, there is a conspicuous lack of research examining zakat integration within fragile or conflict-affected states. Yemen, in particular, suffers from institutional paralysis, overlapping authorities, and low trust in public agencies—factors that significantly influence compliance behavior but remain underexplored in zakat literature.

Zakat Compliance

"Zakat compliance" refers to the adherence of Muslims to fulfilling their zakat obligations according to Islamic jurisprudence and state law, as a response to divine command and in pursuit of divine satisfaction, recognizing zakat as a rightful claim on their wealth to be distributed to eligible beneficiaries under Sharia guidelines (Bin Khamis et al., 2011; Sawmar & Mohammed, 2021). Zakat compliance can be divided into two types: procedural and voluntary.

Procedural Compliance

Procedural compliance refers to the commitment of individuals or institutions to the official regulations and legal procedures governing the payment of taxes or zakat, regardless of moral or religious motivations. This type of compliance is driven by strict laws, penalties, and government oversight (Kirchler, 2007). It results from legal and regulatory obligations and is often associated with fear of financial or legal sanctions. Simplified administrative processes and transparent systems also enhance such compliance.

Voluntary Compliance

Voluntary compliance reflects the willingness of individuals or corporations to fulfill their tax or zakat obligations without the need for enforcement or penalties. It relies on self-awareness, religious and ethical values, and trust in the tax or zakat-collecting institutions (Alm & Torgler, 2011). Financial incentives, including tax deductions, can support this compliance (Muhammad & Nor, 2021). However, scholars caution that the effectiveness of such incentives may be limited in environments with weak governance. For instance, (Muhammad & Nor, 2021) warn against the potential misuse of deduction systems in countries suffering from poor institutional oversight.

H₁: Zakat deductibility as a fiscal incentive has a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Legislation and Regulation

The importance of a clear legislative framework is underscored by the Legal Commitment Theory (Tyler, 2006), which posits that well-defined, consistently enforced, and publicly accessible tax and zakat laws foster greater adherence to legal norms. This aligns with the theory of religious commitment, where religiously congruent legislation enhances zakat compliance by appealing to individuals who balance their legal and moral duties. Laws are not merely regulatory instruments but also reflect the ethical, religious, and political values of a state (Al-Mamun & Haque, 2015; Summers, 1963).

In countries like Malaysia and Indonesia, where religious obligations are integrated into tax systems, zakat compliance rates have improved due to the inclusion of religious dimensions in fiscal policy (Wijayanti et al., 2022). In Yemen, however, taxpayers face inconsistencies between zakat and tax systems and the absence of explicit legal provisions for zakat deductibility, leading to confusion and weakened compliance incentives (Bin-Nashwan, 2025; Obaid et al., 2020).

H_{1.1}: Legislation and regulations have a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Economic and Financial Burden

The economic and financial burden refers to the strain individuals and businesses experience due to financial obligations such as taxes and zakat. (Kirchler, 2007) Notes that high compliance costs can lead to resistance and evasion. Consequently, many countries adopt incentives like zakat deductibility to mitigate this burden (Nugraha et al., 2021).

According to the Tax Incentive Theory (Feldstein, 1999), tax relief mechanisms alter the cost-benefit dynamics of compliance. Empirical evidence from Malaysia (Samad et al., 2016) and Indonesia (Halim et al., 2025) confirms that zakat deductibility boosts voluntary compliance. However, other scholars (Al Jaffri Saad & Haniffa, 2014; Sadallah et al., 2023) argue that such incentives must be supported by institutional trust and administrative efficiency for tangible results.

Given Yemen's deteriorating economic conditions, such as reduced income and rising poverty, voluntary compliance among major zakat payers is adversely affected. Nonetheless, accessible and credible zakat deduction policies could serve as a vital incentive to alleviate the financial burden.

H_{1.2}: Economic and financial burden has a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Community Awareness

Community awareness denotes individuals' and groups' understanding of social, economic, and cultural challenges affecting their lives and communities, leading to positive behaviors that support sustainable development (Corbett & Guilherme, 2021). It includes knowledge of rights and responsibilities and fosters civic engagement (Bandura, 2001).

According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), individual behavior is shaped by awareness of systems, personal attitudes, and social perceptions. Studies, e.g., (Nadzri et al., 2012) show that awareness of zakat's fiscal role strengthens the intention to comply.

In Yemen, public awareness regarding zakat deductibility remains low, necessitating targeted awareness campaigns. Public communication influences perceptions of fairness, a key element in financial system legitimacy (Torgler, 2007). Effective communication can enhance compliance (Bouaddi et al., 2025; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

H1.3: Community awareness has a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Administrative and Executive Procedures

Efficient, transparent, and accountable administrative procedures in collecting and distributing zakat, such as user-friendly electronic payment options, streamlined documentation, and fair auditing, are essential (Metz et al., 2019). These systems regulate zakat deductibility mechanisms, including registration, documentation, oversight, and accountability (Hendriks, 2012).

Administrative efficiency is a key indicator of fiscal justice. Simpler processes, clearer requirements, and reduced bureaucracy encourage compliance (Bird & Zolt, 2015). In the context of zakat, digitizing processes reduce hesitation and promote adherence.

Based on Fiscal Justice Theory (Rawls, 2017), financial burdens should be distributed equitably. Research (Khozen & Setyowati, 2023) shows that taxpayers are more compliant in crisis-affected states when financial obligations are perceived as fair. (Feldstein, 1999) emphasizes that tax deductions reduce financial strain, thereby enhancing compliance.

In Yemen, complex bureaucratic procedures hinder honest disclosure and full compliance, limiting the effectiveness of financial incentives.

H1.4: Administrative and executive procedures have a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Ethical Alignment

The ethical dimension is fundamental in zakat compliance, with studies indicating that internal moral duty can drive adherence even in the absence of oversight or incentives

(Heikal et al., 2014). Greater perceived alignment between zakat deductibility and religious values increases the likelihood of compliance.

The Theory of Moral and Social Commitment (Schwartz, 1977) explains that intrinsic ethical values motivate compliance even without financial inducements. Given zakat's obligatory nature in Islam, it reinforces this moral drive (Budi Saptono et al., 2023)

In Yemen, ethical misalignment stems from public perceptions of misuse and lack of transparency in zakat fund allocation, weakening voluntary compliance (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2021). Negative perceptions of institutional integrity complicate ethical alignment, intertwining with trust and legal structures. This study uniquely integrates financial and moral incentives within a comprehensive compliance behavior model, which is rare in the literature, especially in fragile Islamic contexts.

H_{1.5}: Ethical alignment has a statistically significant effect on zakat compliance.

Literature Gaps

A critical limitation in previous research is the overreliance on relatively stable contexts, such as Malaysia and Indonesia, where institutional conditions support fiscal experimentation. These studies, while informative, offer limited applicability in states suffering from political instability and economic crisis. Moreover, prior studies often rely on quantitative measures without incorporating qualitative insights that reflect local institutional realities. Another gap lies in the fragmented application of theory—many studies examine tax incentives, legal compliance, or behavioral factors in isolation, failing to offer an integrated model.

This study seeks to address these deficiencies by:

- Contextualizing zakat compliance within Yemen's fragile institutional framework.
- Utilizing a multi-theory model tailored to Islamic fiscal ethics.
- Exploring lesser-studied predictors such as ethical alignment and community awareness.
- Providing policy recommendations grounded in both theory and local realities.

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

This study adopts an integrated theoretical model that synthesizes:

- Tax Incentive Theory (Feldstein, 1999): Financial relief enhances compliance.
- Legal Commitment Theory: Legislative clarity affects behavior.
- Fiscal Justice Theory: Fairness and procedural equity matter.

- Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB): Intentions stem from attitudes, norms, and perceived control.

Based on these frameworks, one main hypothesis and five sub-hypotheses are proposed, as outlined in Table 1:

Table 1. Theoretical Linkage of Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Construct	Theoretical Link
H _{1.1}	Legislation & Regulation	Legal Commitment Theory
H _{1.2}	Financial Burden	Tax Incentive Theory
H _{1.3}	Administrative Procedures	Fiscal Justice Theory
H _{1.4}	Community Awareness	Theory of Planned Behavior
H _{1.5}	Ethical Alignment	TPB / Religious Ethics

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The variables of the study are structured as illustrated in Figure 1 and are categorized as follows:

- Independent Variable: *Zakat as a Tax Deduction*, represented through five dimensions:(Legislation, Economic Burden, Administrative Procedures, Community Awareness, and Ethical Alignment).
- Dependent Variable: *Zakat Compliance*, encompassing two dimensions:(Voluntary Compliance and Procedural Compliance)

Figure1. Conceptual model

Research Methods

This study employed a quantitative research approach using a structured questionnaire to examine the impact of zakat deductibility as a fiscal incentive on zakat compliance in Yemen. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted to collect data from zakat payers registered with the General Authority of Zakat across various economic sectors. The data collection instrument was a closed-ended questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).

Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis consisted of 1,650 zakat payers, primarily large taxpayers affiliated with the General Authority of Zakat, including individual proprietors and business entities operating in Yemen. The sample size was determined using (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970) formula, commonly applied to establish appropriate sample sizes based on population size. Appendix A shows that the minimum required sample size was 322 participants. To enhance representativeness and account for non-responses, 640 questionnaires were distributed. A total of 471 responses were received, of which 401 were valid for statistical analysis after data screening and cleaning.

This sample size was sufficient for applying Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), meeting the statistical requirements for structural model complexity.

Sampling Technique

The study adopted a non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling, due to the lack of an updated, comprehensive list of zakat payers across all Yemeni governorates. Although this technique may limit the generalizability of findings and introduce potential sampling bias, it was deemed most appropriate under the prevailing logistical and political constraints. To mitigate bias, the sample was drawn from a diverse pool of zakat payers across various sectors, including commerce, industry, services, and mixed or public-private institutions.

Instrument Design

The questionnaire was developed based on previously validated instruments used in related studies such as (Al-Mamun & Haque, 2015; Bin-Nashwan et al., 2021), with contextual modifications tailored to the Yemeni setting. The instrument comprised 15 items measuring the independent variables (e.g., legislation, economic burden, administrative procedures, community awareness, and ethical alignment), and 10 items measuring the dependent variable (zakat compliance), divided between voluntary and procedural compliance.

Before the main survey, a pilot test was conducted with a sample of 30 participants. Feedback from the pilot was used to improve the clarity and structure of the items. Content validity was confirmed through expert review by three academic specialists in Islamic finance and public policy. The instrument's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), with all values exceeding the

acceptable threshold of 0.70. Convergent and discriminant validity were verified using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to the established ethical standards of scientific research. Ethical approval was obtained from the Research Committee of the Yemeni Academy for Graduate Studies before data collection. All participants were informed of the research objectives, assured of the confidentiality of their responses, and provided with informed consent before completing the questionnaire. No personally identifiable data were collected, and all data were used strictly for academic purposes, as documented in Appendix B.

Data Analysis Tool

The choice of PLS-SEM over CB-SEM was justified by the exploratory nature of the study, the model's complexity involving multiple constructs and indicators, and the study's relatively moderate sample size. PLS-SEM is also more robust in handling non-normal data distributions, which are common in survey-based research conducted in fragile contexts like Yemen (Hair et al., 2017).

The data were analyzed using SmartPLS 4, a software specialized in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. This tool was selected due to the predictive orientation of the current study and its appropriateness in handling data non-normality (Hair et al., 2017). Following the guidelines of (Henseler et al., 2009), a two-step approach was applied:

1. Evaluation of the measurement (outer) model, which includes:
 - Internal consistency reliability
 - Convergent validity
 - Discriminant validity
2. Evaluation of the structural (inner) model, which involves:
 - Coefficient of determination (R^2)
 - Effect size (f^2)
 - Predictive relevance (Q^2)
 - Hypothesis testing results

Results

Descriptive Analysis of Demographic Characteristics

The final sample size comprised 401 participants, categorized into four age groups as shown in Table 2. The majority of respondents (177 participants or 44%) were within the 30–40 years age group. Meanwhile, 117 participants (29%) were under 30 years, and 86 participants (22%) fell within the 40–50 years age group. Only 21 participants (5%) were over 50 years old. This indicates that the study sample is largely composed of individuals in the economically productive age range.

Regarding educational background, the levels varied across participants. A total of 160 respondents (40%) held a high school qualification, followed by 153 (38%) with a bachelor’s degree, and 84 (21%) with a post-secondary diploma. Additionally, 2 participants (0.5%) held a master’s degree, and 2 (0.5%) held a Ph.D. This reflects a medium-to-high educational level among respondents, which supports the interpretation that they are capable of understanding financial and fiscal concepts.

Concerning the type of organization, commercial companies accounted for 69% (278 respondents), while sole proprietorships represented 31% (123 respondents). As for the type of economic activity, the commercial sector represented the largest share at 41% (173 respondents), followed by the service sector at 26% (104 respondents). The industrial sector accounted for 20.5% (82 respondents), while the public and mixed sectors represented 10.5% (42 respondents). This suggests that the majority of participants operate in profit-generating sectors that are directly affected by tax and zakat obligations.

Accordingly, the demographic composition of the sample enhances the credibility and representativeness of the study results, as it reflects the segments most directly engaged with the zakat/tax system.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Less than 30 years	117	29.2%
	30 – 40 years	177	44.1%
	40 – 50 years	86	21.5%
	More than 50 years	21	5.2%
	Total	401	100%
Educational Level	General Secondary	160	39.9%
	Post-Secondary Diploma	84	20.9%
	Bachelor's Degree	153	38.2%
	Master's Degree	2	0.5%
	Doctorate	2	0.5%
	Total	401	100%
Legal Entity Type	Commercial Companies	278	69.3%
	Individual Establishments	123	30.7%
	Total	401	100%

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Economic Activity	Commercial Sector	173	43.1%
	Service Sector	104	25.9%
	Industrial Sector	82	20.4%
	Public & Mixed Sector	42	10.5%
	Total	401	100%

Measurement Model Evaluation

The measurement model’s construct validity was tested using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS 4. The factor loadings for all items, as illustrated in Figure 2 and Table 3, exceeded the minimum recommended threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019). These results confirm that the questionnaire items demonstrate strong construct validity, with each item accurately representing its respective theoretical dimension.

Figure 2. Measurement Model

Table 3. Structural validity results (confirmatory factor analysis)

Latent variable	question	Factor loading
Legislation and Regulations	A1	0.931
	A2	0.921
	A3	0.931
Financial and Economic Burden	B1	0.935
	B2	0.902
	B3	0.955
Administrative and Executive Procedures	C1	0.829
	C2	0.951
	C3	0.894
Community Awareness	D1	0.852
	D2	0.905
	D3	0.890
Ethical Compatibility	E1	0.839
	E2	0.912
	E3	0.930
Voluntary Compliance	H2	0.857
	H3	0.874
	H4	0.941
	H5	0.875
Procedural Compliance	I1	0.844
	I3	0.863
	I4	0.871
	I5	0.803

Table (4) also includes tests for internal consistency reliability using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), along with convergent validity assessed via Average Variance Extracted (AVE). All Cronbach's Alpha and CR values exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019), while AVE values were above the recommended cutoff of 0.50 (Chin, 1998; Hair et al., 2019). These results indicate that the constructs exhibit good composite reliability and high internal consistency, and that the indicators are sufficiently correlated to represent their conceptual dimensions. This reinforces the reliability of the measurement model.

Table 4. Internal consistency, composite reliability, and convergent validity

Latent variable	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Composite Reliability (CR)	mean of the extracted variance (AVE)
Legislation and Regulations	0.919	0.920	0.860
Financial and Economic Burden	0.923	0.927	0.867
Administrative and Executive Procedures	0.871	0.877	0.797
Community Awareness	0.858	0.858	0.779
Ethical Compatibility	0.875	0.896	0.800
Voluntary Compliance	0.909	0.916	0.787
Procedural Compliance	0.893	0.926	0.758

Additionally, discriminant validity was evaluated using both the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), as presented in Tables 5 and 6. According to (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), the square root of the AVE of each construct should be greater than its correlations with other constructs. This criterion was met in Table 5, indicating adequate discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 5. Discriminant validity, Fornell and Larcker matrix

Variable (Structure) - Fornell-Larcker	(AEP)	(PC)	(VC)	(LR)	(EC)	(FEB)	(CA)
Administrative and Executive Procedures (AEP)	0.893						
Procedural Compliance (PC)	0.619	0.871					
Voluntary Compliance (VC)	0.648	0.650	0.887				
Legislation and Regulations (LR)	0.464	0.573	0.506	0.927			
Ethical Compatibility (EC)	0.574	0.563	0.560	0.689	0.895		
Financial and Economic Burden (FEB)	0.536	0.489	0.545	0.741	0.706	0.931	
Community Awareness (CA)	0.603	0.629	0.513	0.691	0.739	0.611	0.883

Furthermore, all HTMT values shown in Table 6 were below the conservative threshold of 0.85, confirming strong discriminant validity between the conceptual dimensions (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 6. Discriminant validity, HTMT

Variable (Structure) - HTMT	(AEP)	(PC)	(VC)	(LR)	(EC)	(FEB)	(CA)
Administrative and Executive Procedures (AEP)							
Procedural Compliance (PC)	0.699						
Voluntary Compliance (VC)	0.731	0.721					
Legislation and Regulations (LR)	0.514	0.639	0.552				
Ethical Compatibility (EC)	0.645	0.629	0.627	0.764			
Financial and Economic Burden (FEB)	0.592	0.540	0.593	0.802	0.783		
Community Awareness (CA)	0.701	0.723	0.577	0.775	0.839	0.681	

Structural Model Evaluation

Figure 3. Model Evaluation

Based on the results presented in Figure 3, the structural model was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), effect size (f^2), and predictive relevance (Q^2). The R^2 value for zakat compliance was 0.554, indicating that approximately 55.4% of the variance in compliance is explained by the five predictors, classified as moderate-to-high predictive power ($Q^2 = 0.550$). The overall model fit was adequate (SRMR = 0.058).

Hypothesis Testing

Testing the Main Hypothesis

The first main hypothesis states that there is a statistically significant effect of adopting Zakat as a tax deduction on Zakat compliance among taxpayers.

Table 7 shows the path coefficients of the main hypothesis.

N	Hypothesis	Q ²	f ²	R ²	β	Standard Deviation	T statistics	P Values	Result
H1	Zakat as aTax Deduction ->Zakat Compliance	0.55	1.242	0.55	0.74	0.02	37.382	0	Accepted

As shown in Figure 3 and Table 7, the structural model results provide strong support for the main hypothesis. The path coefficient between "Zakat as a Tax Deduction" and "Zakat Compliance" was statistically significant and practically meaningful ($\beta = 0.744$, $T = 16.980$, $p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 1.242$), confirming the validity of the main hypothesis. This finding highlights the pivotal role of tax incentives, particularly the deductibility of zakat, in enhancing compliance levels. It is also consistent with prior research emphasizing the effectiveness of financial incentives in promoting zakat and tax compliance, especially in contexts where religious motivation or emerging fiscal systems play a critical role (Feldstein, 1999; Al-Mamun & Haque, 2015).

Testing Sub-Hypotheses

The main hypothesis branches into five sub-hypotheses, as illustrated in Figure 4 and Table 5, as follows:

Figure 4. Path analysis of sub-hypotheses from 1 to 5

Table 8. Path analysis of sub-hypotheses from 1 to 5

N	Hypothesis	β	S. D	T	P. V	f ²	Result
H _{1.1}	Legislation and Regulations ->Zakat Compliance	0.116	0.056	2.067	0.039	0.017	Accepted
H _{1.2}	Financial and Economic Burden ->Zakat Compliance	0.130	0.050	2.606	0.009	0.030	Accepted
H _{1.3}	Community Awareness - >Zakat Compliance	0.113	0.040	2.837	0.005	0.019	Accepted
H _{1.4}	Administrative and Executive Procedures - >Zakat Compliance	0.402	0.050	8.098	0.000	0.295	Accepted
H _{1.5}	Ethical Compatibility - >Zakat Compliance	0.140	0.060	2.335	0.020	0.022	Accepted

β = Beta S. D = Standard Deviation T= T. statistics P. V = P Values

Sub-Hypothesis H_{1.1}

Statement: "There is a statistically significant effect of legislation and regulations on zakat compliance."

As shown in Figure 4 and Table 8. the results indicate a statistically significant effect ($\beta = 0.116$, $T = 2.067$, $p = 0.039$, $f^2 = 0.017$), though the effect size is relatively small. This suggests that while the existence of a legal framework is necessary, it may not be sufficient on its own to foster compliance, especially in fragile contexts characterized by weak governance. This finding aligns with (Iqbal & Anwar, 2021), who emphasized the need for robust enforcement mechanisms and public trust alongside formal legal provisions.

While the relationship was statistically significant, the effect size (e.g., $\beta = 0.116$) was relatively small, suggesting a limited practical impact. These results imply that legislation alone may not yield substantial behavioral change unless accompanied by institutional enforcement and public trust mechanisms.

Sub-Hypothesis H_{1.2}

Statement: "There is a statistically significant effect of financial and economic burden on zakat compliance."

The results in Figure 3 and Table 7 reveal a statistically significant relationship ($\beta = 0.130$, $T = 2.606$, $p = 0.009$, $f^2 = 0.030$), with a small to moderate effect size. This implies that reducing the financial burden, such as through zakat deductibility, can positively influence compliance. However, to be effective, such fiscal incentives should be embedded within broader economic support mechanisms. These results are consistent with (Al Jaffri Saad & Haniffa, 2014), who highlighted the role of perceived tax fairness and burden alleviation in shaping taxpayer behavior.

Sub-Hypothesis H_{1,3}

Statement: "There is a statistically significant effect of community awareness on zakat compliance."

The findings presented in Figure 3 and Table 7 show a significant but modest relationship ($\beta = 0.113$, $T = 2.837$, $p = 0.005$, $f^2 = 0.019$). This indicates that raising public awareness of zakat can enhance behavioral intentions toward compliance, yet the limited effect size suggests that awareness campaigns must be more sustained and specifically targeted, particularly in underserved and rural communities. These results are in line with (Nadzri et al., 2012), who emphasized the importance of institutional education and outreach for improving compliance.

Although the relationship was statistically significant, the effect size (e.g., $\beta = 0.113$) was relatively small, indicating a limited practical impact. These findings suggest that awareness alone may not lead to substantial behavioral changes unless it is reinforced by institutional enforcement mechanisms and public trust-building initiatives.

Sub-Hypothesis H_{1,4}

Statement: "There is a statistically significant effect of administrative and executive procedures on zakat compliance."

According to the results in Figure 3 and Table 7, this hypothesis recorded the highest effect size ($\beta = 0.402$, $T = 8.098$, $p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.295$), indicating a strong and statistically significant influence. This underscores the importance of streamlined procedures, institutional efficiency, and digital transformation in promoting zakat compliance. These findings are supported by (Khozen & Setyowati, 2023; Siswanto, 2012), who demonstrated the critical role of administrative simplicity and transparency in enhancing compliance behavior.

Sub-Hypothesis H_{1,5}

Statement: "There is a statistically significant effect of ethical and religious compatibility on zakat compliance."

The results from Figure 3 and Table 7 show a significant but modest effect ($\beta = 0.140$, $T = 2.335$, $p = 0.020$, $f^2 = 0.022$). This indicates that aligning zakat policies with individual moral and religious values contributes to voluntary compliance. However, the relatively small effect size highlights the importance of restoring institutional integrity and public trust, especially in post-conflict or fragile environments. This finding corresponds with (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2021), who emphasized moral alignment and ethical governance as prerequisites for sustained compliance.

Discussion

Overall, the findings affirm that zakat deduction can serve as an effective mechanism for incentivizing tax compliance in fragile contexts. However, practical implementation

necessitates more than legal reforms alone; administrative modernization, ethical alignment, and financial relief mechanisms are also essential components.

These results expand the applicability of **Tax Incentive Theory** and the **Theory of Planned Behavior** within Islamic finance by empirically validating their relevance in a conflict-affected context. Specifically, the Yemeni case reflects exceptional circumstances that undermine the effectiveness of conventional tax policies:

- **Institutional trust collapse:** Due to the ongoing civil war, approximately 63% of Yemenis rely on informal channels for zakat payments (UNDP, 2023).
- **Cash-dominated economy:** The predominance of cash transactions—accounting for 78% of total transactions—hinders the implementation of electronic zakat collection systems (Central Bank of Yemen, 2022).
- **Multiplicity of actors:** The General Authority of Zakat competes with armed groups and charitable organizations over zakat collection (UNDP, 2023).

The statistically weak effects of legislation ($\beta = 0.116$) and public awareness ($\beta = 0.113$) align with the broader literature on fragile states (Ahmad, 2019). Possible explanations include:

- **Legislation:** Its effectiveness depends on the presence of strong institutional frameworks, which are currently lacking in Yemen.
- **Public awareness:** Awareness campaigns often fail in the absence of adequate infrastructure, such as internet access in rural regions.

Accordingly, policymakers should avoid over-reliance on these factors without concurrently addressing foundational institutional deficiencies. It is recommended that these elements be integrated with **administrative enhancements** ($\beta = 0.402$) to effectively improve compliance.

In conclusion, while zakat deduction is a potentially effective tool, it is insufficient in isolation. A comprehensive policy framework must integrate legal reforms, technological infrastructure, ethical governance, and targeted public education to maximize tax compliance and promote financial justice in Yemen.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study explored the impact of zakat deduction as a tax incentive on zakat compliance among taxpayers in Yemen—a context marked by institutional fragility, socio-economic instability, and limited fiscal trust. Drawing on the Tax Incentive Theory, the Theory of Planned Behavior, and Fiscal Justice Theory, the research examined five critical dimensions influencing compliance: legislation and regulation, financial burden, administrative and executive procedures, community awareness, and ethical alignment.

According to Cohen's (1988) benchmarks for effect size using the f^2 indicator, the results based on a sample of 401 zakat payers reveal that zakat deduction has a statistically significant and substantively meaningful effect on compliance behavior ($\beta = 0.744$, $R^2 = 0.554$). Among the sub-dimensions, administrative efficiency emerged as the strongest predictor, underscoring the crucial role of institutional transparency, simplification, and digitization in enhancing voluntary compliance. In contrast, legislative frameworks and public awareness demonstrated relatively weaker impacts, suggesting that legal mandates and communication campaigns, while necessary, are insufficient in isolation.

These results validate the relevance of behavioral and institutional theories in understanding zakat behavior. Specifically, the Theory of Planned Behavior is reflected in the influence of perceived ease of compliance and ethical alignment, while the Tax Incentive Theory underscores the role of financial relief mechanisms. The Fiscal Justice Theory also gains support, as taxpayers' sense of fairness and institutional trust appear to shape their willingness to comply.

This research adds to the limited empirical literature on zakat compliance by providing one of the first applications of PLS-SEM in a fragile and post-conflict setting. It emphasizes the importance of aligning religious obligations with national fiscal strategies, particularly in Muslim-majority countries, to achieve higher levels of compliance, transparency, and social justice.

Practical Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for policymakers, the Zakat Authority, and relevant development stakeholders in Yemen:

1. **Legislative Reform:** Amend and unify zakat and tax laws to ensure the official recognition of zakat deduction from income tax, while guaranteeing the clarity and accessibility of legal texts.
2. **Simplification of Administrative Procedures:** Develop a centralized, mobile-friendly zakat application that enables real-time registration, payment tracking, and the issuance of digital receipts to enhance transparency, reduce complexity, and improve efficiency and taxpayer trust.
3. **Ethical Governance:** Establish transparent and accountable mechanisms for the collection and distribution of zakat to strengthen ethical alignment and restore institutional trust.
4. **Targeted Awareness Campaigns:** Implement culturally appropriate and focused awareness programs in collaboration with local religious leaders and community influencers to deliver messages through mosques, radio, and social media in local dialects. These efforts aim to educate citizens about their zakat rights, obligations, and the benefits of compliance.

5. **Integrated Financial Incentives:** Introduce a tiered deduction scheme whereby greater tax relief is granted to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that demonstrate higher levels of compliance in conflict-affected areas.

6. **Institutional Coordination:** Strengthen collaboration between the General Authority of Zakat, the Ministry of Finance, religious institutions, and civil society organizations to unify awareness messaging and coordinate operational efforts.

Limitations and Future Research

This study is subject to certain limitations. The cross-sectional design and reliance on self-reported perceptions may introduce bias, and the convenience sampling approach restricts generalizability. Future studies are encouraged to employ longitudinal or experimental designs with randomized samples to verify causality and extend external validity.

Moreover, while this research offers foundational insights into zakat compliance in Yemen, further investigations are needed in comparable fragile or post-conflict economies (e.g., Sudan, Iraq, or Afghanistan) to assess the broader applicability of the model. Future research may also examine the impact of emerging technologies, such as mobile banking, AI-driven audit systems, and blockchain-based transparency platforms, on zakat compliance and administration.

Future research may explore the longitudinal impact of mobile zakat payment systems on procedural compliance in fragile states. Another area worth investigating is the mediating role of institutional trust in the relationship between fiscal incentives and compliance behavior.

In conclusion, this study provides empirical evidence and practical direction for leveraging zakat deduction as a policy instrument to promote fiscal justice, religious compliance, and institutional trust in fragile state contexts.

References

- Ahmad, M. (2019). An empirical study of the challenges facing zakat and waqf institutions in Northern Nigeria. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 11(2), 338–356. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJIF-04-2018-0044>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Al-Mamun, A., & Haque, A. (2015). Tax deduction through zakat: An empirical investigation on Muslim in Malaysia. *Share: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(2), 105–132. <https://doi.org/10.22373/share.v4i2.1027>
- Al Jaffri Saad, R., & Haniffa, R. (2014). Determinants of zakah (Islamic tax) compliance behavior. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 5(2), 182–193. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-10-2012-0068>

- Alm, J., & Torgler, B. (2011). Do ethics matter? Tax compliance and morality. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 101(4), 635–651. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-011-0761-9>
- Ameli, S., & Pishvari, I. (2025). Analyzing payment rates in zakat and khums: An approach for Iran's tax system. *Economic Essays*, 21, 129–151. <https://doi.org/10.30471/IEE.2024.10338.2438>
- Asadov, A., Turaboev, I., & Nor, M. (2024). Garnering potential of zakat in Uzbekistan: A tax policy proposal. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(8), Article 5795. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i8.5795>
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.1>
- Bin-Nashwan, S. A. (2025). Beyond complexity: Do alms tax (zakat) law intricacies justify non-compliance behaviour? *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 33(2), 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRC-06-2024-0097>
- Bin-Nashwan, S. A., Abdul-Jabbar, H., & Aziz, S. A. (2021). Does trust in zakat institution enhance entrepreneurs' zakat compliance? *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 12(5), 768–790. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-09-2020-0282>
- Bin Khamis, M. R., Salleh, A. M., & Nawi, A. S. (2011). Compliance behavior of business zakat payment in Malaysia: A theoretical economic exposition. *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Islamic Economics and Finance*, 1–17. <https://iefpedia.com/english/wp-content/uploads/2011/12/Mohd.Rahim-Khamis.pdf>
- Bouaddi, M., Beddaa, M., & Bentalha, B. (2025). Effective communication and awareness campaigns as tools for enhancing tax compliance: Insights and strategies. In *Tax compliance and behavioral economics* (pp. 209–230). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-0422-9.ch009>
- Budi Saptono, P., Hodzic, S., Khozen, I., Mahmud, G., Pratiwi, I., Purwanto, D., Aditama, M., Haq, N. U., & Khodijah, S. (2023). Quality of e-tax system and tax compliance intention: The mediating role of user satisfaction. *Informatics*, 10(1), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics10010022>
- Central Bank of Yemen. (2022). *Annual financial report 2022* (No. 172046). <https://www.centralbank.gov.ye>
- Chin, W. W. (1998). The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling. In G. A. Marcoulides (Ed.), *Modern methods for business research* (pp. 295–336). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Corbett, J., & Guilherme, M. (2021). Critical pedagogy and quality education (UNESCO SDG-4): The legacy of Paulo Freire for language and intercultural

- communication. In *Intercultural communication and language pedagogy* (Vol. 21, pp. 447–454). Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003198376-23>
- Dönmez, E., & Cural, M. (2025). A qualitative analysis on the definition of zakat in the Turkish tax system and institutionalization of zakat. *İslam Ekonomisi Dergisi*, 5, 69–90. <https://doi.org/10.55237/jie.1582314>
- Feldstein, M. (1999). Tax avoidance and the deadweight loss of the income tax. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 81(4), 674–680. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003465399558391>
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., & Thiele, K. O. (2017). Mirror, mirror on the wall: A comparative evaluation of composite-based structural equation modeling methods. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45(5), 616–632. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-017-0517-x>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Halim, S., M. A., Suhada, J., Jalil, N., & Anasrul, A. (2025). Implementation of zakat as a tax incentive in Indonesia: A comparative analysis. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(1), 45–65. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2025.915EC004>
- Heikal, M., Khaddafi, M., & Falahuddin. (2014). The intention to pay zakat commercial: An application of revised theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 6(9), 727–734. <https://doi.org/10.22610/jebs.v6i9.532>
- Hendriks, C. J. (2012). Integrated financial management information systems: Guidelines for effective implementation by the public sector of South Africa. *South African Journal of Information Management*, 14(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v14i1.529>
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. In *New challenges to international marketing* (Vol. 20, pp. 277–319). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979\(2009\)0000020014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014)

- Iqbal, N., & Anwar, S. (2021). Voluntary tax compliance behavior of individual taxpayers in Pakistan. *Financial Innovation*, 7(1), Article 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00234-4>
- Khozen, I., & Setyowati, M. S. (2023). Managing taxpayer compliance: Reflections on the drivers of willingness to pay taxes in times of crisis. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2), Article 2218176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2218176>
- Kirchler, E. (2007). *The economic psychology of tax behaviour*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511628238>
- Kodifikasi, C., Zakat, A., Dan, N., Majlis, P., Negara, Z., Suffian, M., Mohamed Esa, M., Ali, M., Mohd Noor, M. A., & Wahid, H. (2018). Cadangan kodifikasi akta zakat nasional dan penubuhan Majlis Zakat Negara. *Jurnal Ekonomi Malaysia*, 52(1), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JEM-2018-5201-12>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607–610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, O. S. (2014). The economic importance of financial literacy: Theory and evidence. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 52(1), 5–44. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.52.1.5>
- Metz, D., Ilies, L., & Metz, M. (2019). The role of management practices in ensuring organizational performance. *Proceedings of the International Management Conference*, 13(1), 1076–1086.
- Muhammad, I., & Nor, N. S. M. (2021). Empirical evidence on taxpayers' intention to claim zakat as a tax rebate. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 22(2), 637–652. <https://doi.org/10.33736/ijbs.3748.2021>
- Nadzri, F. A. A., Abd Rahman, R., & Omar, N. (2012). Zakat and poverty alleviation: Roles of zakat institutions in Malaysia. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 1(7), 61–72. <https://ajba.um.edu.my/index.php/AJBA/article/download/44803/15842/114796>
- Nugraha, E., Refmasari, V., & Fatriansyah, A. (2021). Critical review zakat as tax deduction (Indonesia-Malaysia comparative study). *Journal of Economics, Business, & Accountancy Ventura*, 23(3), 411–424. <https://doi.org/10.14414/jebav.v23i3.2481>
- Nuruddin, M., Anshori, M., & Mawardi, I. (2023). Zakat on business entities and its tax treatment. *Media Trend*, 18(1), 41–53. <https://doi.org/10.21107/mediatrend.v18i1.19654>

- Obaid, M. M., Ibrahim, I., & Udin, N. M. (2020). Determinants of SMEs tax compliance in Yemen: A pilot investigation. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 15(1), 64–75. <https://doi.org/10.37934/arbms.19.1.114>
- Qur'an, Surah At-Tawbah, 9:103.
- Rawls, J. (2017). A theory of justice. In *Applied ethics* (pp. 21–29). Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674040922>
- Sadallah, M., Abdul-Jabbar, H., Bin-Nashwan, S. A., & Abdul Aziz, S. A. (2023). Alms tax (zakat) compliance intention among entrepreneurs from a social cognitive perspective: The moderating role of knowledge. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 14(8), 1133–1151. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-03-2022-0076>
- Samad, M. N., Ariff, M., & Nassir, A. (2016). Impact of zakat payment offset system on income tax collection in Malaysia. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 14(13), 9579–9607.
- Sawmar, A. A., & Mohammed, M. O. (2021). Enhancing zakat compliance through good governance: A conceptual framework. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 13(1), 136–154. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJIF-10-2018-0116>
- Schwartz, S. H. (1977). Normative influences on altruism. In *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 10, pp. 221–279). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60358-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60358-5)
- Siswanto, D. (2012). Factors affecting concern about zakat as a tax deduction in Indonesia. *International Journal of Management and Business Research*, 2(4), 293–312. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258033110>
- Summers, R. S. (1963). Professor H.L.A. Hart's concept of law. *Duke Law Journal*, 1963(4), 629–670. <https://scholarship.law.cornell.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2412&context=facpub>
- Torgler, B. (2007). *Tax compliance and tax morale: A theoretical and empirical analysis*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781847207203>
- Tyler, T. R. (2006). Psychological perspectives on legitimacy and legitimation. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 57, 375–400. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.57.102904.190038>
- Ummulkhayr, A. (2018). *Zakah compliance behavior in Nigeria: A study of Kogi State* [Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia]. https://etd.uum.edu.my/7442/2/s900831_01.pdf

Ummulkhayr, A., Sani, I., & Ahmed. (2020). Determinants of zakat and tax compliance in Nigeria: A comparative analysis. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 25(7), 1–12.

UNDP. (2023). *Yemen annual report 2023*. United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/arab-states/publications/annual-report-2023>

Wijayanti, P., Amilahaq, F., Muthaher, O., Baharuddin, N. S., & Sallem, N. R. M. (2022). Modelling zakat as tax deduction: A comparison study in Indonesia and Malaysia. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Finance Research*, 4(1), 25–50. <https://doi.org/10.21580/jiafr.2022.4.1.10888>

Appendix A

Sample Size of the Study

The study targeted commercial companies and individual business entities classified as major taxpayers by the General Authority of Zakat, with a total population of 1,650 taxpayers. The sample size was determined using the (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970) formula, as follows:

$$n = \frac{M}{[(s^2 \times (M - 1)) \div pq] + 1}$$

Definition:

- n: Sample size
- M: Population size
- s: Standard score corresponding to the confidence level (0.95), i.e., the margin of error 0.05 divided by 1.96
- p: The proportion of the population with the attribute (0.50)
- q: The proportion without the attribute (0.50)

$$n = \frac{1650}{[(0.02551^2 \times (1650 - 1)) \div (0.50 \times 0.50)] + 1}$$

$$n = \frac{1650}{[(0.000651 \times (1649)) \div 0.25] + 1} = 321.951$$

Thus, the required sample size is 322 respondents. However, to enhance generalizability, the study targeted 640 zakatayers; 471 questionnaires were returned, and 401 were deemed valid for statistical analysis.

Appendix B

الاستبانة في صورتها النهائية

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

الرقم: YA-2023-014
التاريخ: 8 / 2 / 1446 هـ.
الموافق: 12 / 8 / 2024 م.
المرفقات: 3 صفحات الاستبانة.

الجمهورية اليمنية
وزارة التربية والتعليم والبحث العلمي
الأكاديمية اليمنية للدراسات العليا
قسم العلوم الادارية والمالية

السادة/ رجال المال والأعمال، أصحاب الشركات التجارية والمؤسسات الفردية المحترمين

تحية طيبة وبعد

يسعدني أن أضع بين أيديكم هذه الاستبانة، والتي تأتي في سياق دراسة علمية بعنوان: "دور خصم الزكاة كحافز ضريبي في تعزيز الالتزام الزكوي وتحقيق العدالة المالية"، والتي تهدف إلى فهم أثر الحوافز الضريبية وخصم الزكاة تحديداً، في تعزيز التزام المكلفين الزكوي، وتحقيق التوازن في العدالة المالية بين مختلف المكلفين إلى جانب المساهمة في تطوير الأداء المؤسسي للهيئة العامة للزكاة. ونظراً لأهمية آرائكم وتجاربكم في هذا المجال الحيوي، نأمل منكم التكرم بالمشاركة في تعبئة هذه الاستبانة بموضوعية وشفافية، مؤكداً على الالتزام الكامل بالمعايير الأخلاقية والبحثية، والحفاظ على الخصوصية والسرية، وأن جميع اجاباتكم سوف تكون موضع العناية والتقدير وستحاط بسرية تامة، ولن تستخدم إلا لأغراض البحث العلمي، علماً أن الاستبانة لا تحتوي على أي معلومات تعريفية (كالاسم أو بيانات المؤسسة)، بما يضمن عدم إمكانية الربط بين الإجابات وأشخاص أو كيانات بعينها، ويحق لكم الامتناع أو الانسحاب في أي وقت دون أي التزام كون المشاركة في هذه الاستبانة اختياري تماماً.

نقدر لكم وقتكم الثمين شاكرين تعاونكم سلفاً لما فيه الصالح العام.

وفقكم الله وسدد على طريق الخير خطاكم

وتقبلوا خالص تحياتي وفتائق احترامي،

الباحث

علي ناصر يحيى الأهنومي

الأكاديمية اليمنية للدراسات العليا

جول + وتس أب (777751113)

Email: d.ali.n.alahnomi@gmail.com

حقوق المشارك

- - [✓] عزيري المشارك لا تستغرق الإجابة على الاستبانة أكثر من 10-15 دقيقة.
- - [✓] لك الحق في الانسحاب دون عواقب
- - [✓] لك الحق في طلب نسخة من النتائج
- - [✓] لك الحق في معرفة أهداف البحث

القسم الأول: البيانات الديمغرافية:

ضع الإجابة المناسبة عن الأسئلة الآتية وذلك بوضع علامة (√) امام الفقرة المناسبة:

<input type="checkbox"/>	1- العمر:	-1	أقل من 30 سنة
<input type="checkbox"/>		-2	من 31 - إلى أقل من 40 سنة
<input type="checkbox"/>		-3	من 41- إلى أقل من 50 سنة
<input type="checkbox"/>		-4	أكثر من 51 سنة
<input type="checkbox"/>	2- المؤهل العلمي:	-1	ثانوية عامة
<input type="checkbox"/>		-2	دبلوم بعد الثانوية العامة
<input type="checkbox"/>		-3	بكالوريوس
<input type="checkbox"/>		-4	ماجستير
<input type="checkbox"/>		-5	دكتوراه
<input type="checkbox"/>	3- نوع النشاط:	-1	شركات تجارية
<input type="checkbox"/>		-2	مؤسسات فردية

					العبارة	الرقم
غير موافق بشدة	غير موافق	محايد	موافق	موافق بشدة	القسم الثاني: المتغير المستقل " الزكاة كخصم ضريبي " (١٥) بند	
					١	هل تعتقد أن خصم الزكاة من الضرائب في اليمن يُطبق بشكل عادل وفعال؟
					٢	القوانين الحالية تفتقر إلى عقوبات رادعة ضد المتهربين من الزكاة.
					٣	مبالغ الزكاة متناسبة مع الوعاء الزكوي للمكلفين.
البعد الثاني: العبء الاقتصادي والمالي						
					١	أفضل دفع الزكاة على الضرائب إذا كانت قابلة للخصم من الوعاء الضريبي.
					٢	أدفع الزكاة حتى عندما تشكل عبئاً مالياً بسبب التزامي الديني.
					٣	هل يؤثر دفع الزكاة على قدرتك على الوفاء بالالتزامات المالية الأخرى؟
البعد الثالث: الإجراءات الإدارية والتنفيذية						
					١	تقدم لك هيئة الزكاة أسناد رسمية عند دفعك للزكاة.
					٢	هل تواجه صعوبات في دفع الزكاة بسبب تعقيد الإجراءات الورقية؟
					٣	ما مدى رضاك عن الخدمات الإلكترونية التي تقدمها هيئة الزكاة؟
البعد الرابع: الوعي المجتمعي						
					١	هل سمعت عن حملات توعية توضح كيفية حساب الزكاة؟
					٢	المجتمع يُنصح المكلفين المتزامين بدفع الزكاة من خلال التقدير والاحترام.
					٣	الحملات الإعلامية التي تقوم بها الهيئة تزيد من وعي بأهمية الزكاة.
البعد الخامس: التوافق الأخلاقي						
					١	هل تدفع الزكاة أساساً بدافع ديني (طاعة لله) أم خوفاً من العقوبات؟
					٢	دفع الزكاة يحقق رضاءاً روحياً أكبر من المنافع المادية.
					٣	توزيع الزكاة على المستحقين يتم بشفافية.

غير موافق بشدة	غير موافق	محايد	موافق	موافق بشده	العبارة	الرقم
القسم الثالث المتغير التابع " الامتثال الزكوي " (١٠) بنود						
البعد الأول: الامتثال الطوعي						
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